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DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES STAGES AND ITS SITUATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article seeks to highlight the essence, origin and stages of development of information technology, their role in the transition to the digital economy and the state of the digital economy in Uzbekistan, measures taken to develop it and the issues to be addressed.

Keywords: information, technology, information technology, computer technology, electronic technology, digital technology, digital economy, globalization, artificial intelligence, internet, mobile communications.

Introduction.

Information technology is the foundation for the transition to the digital economy. Full demonstration of the socio-economic potential of information technology and its introduction into all sectors of the national economy remains the most pressing issue in the current process of globalization. There are a number of pending tasks to reveal the essence of these processes and convey their importance to users.

At the same time, given the international significance of this issue in the current context of globalization, it is necessary to further develop cooperation with the world community to better understand the essence of the concepts related to the main directions and problems of the digital sector. The main task is to carry out work in this direction in accordance with the requirements of the times.

In recent years, various groups of experts from around the world have been offering highly effective and up-to-date recommendations on advanced development modules, including the development of each country's national economy on the basis of digital technologies. Without it, we could leave humanity without the benefits of digital technology.

In many countries around the world, great strides have been made in digital technology. This creates ample opportunities for businesses, as well as people, not only to enter the world of the computer and its modern form, the Internet, and to use its services effectively. After all, it is hard to imagine our lifestyle today without the services of information technology.

It is becoming a natural process for the digital economy to serve the common interests of the people and to cover all aspects on a large scale. Such an economy

requires a lot of new knowledge and skills, radically new measures of social protection, a qualitatively new relationship between work and leisure.

The search for new solutions requires the cooperation of governments, civil society, political circles and the scientific community to create modern technologies. This means that digital technologies will serve to further expand economic ties between countries and regions.

In our country, comprehensive measures are being taken to actively develop the digital economy, the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies in all sectors and industries, especially in public administration, education, health, industry and agriculture. The adoption of the National Program of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" on October 5, 2020 is a clear proof of our opinion.

According to the program, more than 220 priority projects have been launched to improve the e-government system, further develop the local market of software products and information technologies, establish IT parks in all regions of the country, as well as provide qualified personnel for all sectors of the national economy. Such positive changes will undoubtedly serve for a more prosperous and prosperous life of our people.

Analysis of the relevant literature.

The essence of information technology, the history of its origin and issues of their further development were discussed by foreign scientists Gromov G.R. (Informatsionnye tekhnologii epoxi Interneta.-M.: Nauka, 2004), Oleynik A.I. (IT - Infrastructure.-M.: ID High School Economics, 2012), Wolfson M.B. (Organization of electronic business: Uchebnoe posobie.-SPb: SPbGUT, 2014), Lapidus L.V. (Digital economy: management of electronic business and electronic commerce.-M.: INFRA, 2019) Artyushina L.A., Troitskaya E.A. Informatsionnye tekhnologii elektronnoy biznesa.-Vladimir, 2019 and others are reflected in scientific research.

One of our local scientists, Gulomov S.S., spoke about the state of the digital economy in Uzbekistan and its development. (Blockchain technologies in the digital economy. - T., 2019), Abdullaev O.M. (Digital Economy.-T., 2020), Jumanazarov Q. S. (Digital Economy. - Karshi, 2021) and others.

Research methodology.

The methodological basis of this research was formed as a result of the study of published theoretical and practical information on information technology, relevant laws and other documents. However, in the scientific observation of the research, historical and logical, methods of analysis and synthesis were used.

Analysis and results.

The information environment consists of three interconnected components. These are: user information structure, information technology, objects involved in management. In this article, we want to focus on issues related to information technology and its history of development.

When it comes to information technology, information is involved both as a material and as a product and in delivering information to users. It is a qualitatively new information about an object, process or event, and the technology is reflected in the employee's way of working with information and his attitude to technical means.

It can be said that information technology came into being several million years ago with the emergence of the first methods of interaction between human beings (making different sounds, gestures, actions). In this case, the exchange of information was carried out only between individuals. With the advent of speech (about 100,000 years ago), there was an opportunity for information to accumulate in the human brain.

The advent of writing led to the emergence of a common memory of people and made it possible to carry out a complete process such as collecting, transmitting, processing, storing and transmitting information, i.e. information began to be recorded on material carriers. The subsequent development of the emerging information system and technology began to take place mainly in connection with the means of communication.

The development of information technology, in addition to the system of information presentation, was associated with the improvement of information and communication tools. They are the intangible carrier of information, i.e., they emerged after speech emerged. This can be considered as the first step in the history of information technology development.

With the development of information technology, the era of creating a universal system for receiving, storing and fast transmission of information in a user-friendly form has begun. This has made information a driving force of technical, social and economic development and has defined its leading force in the modern technical revolution.

In the fourth millennium BC, writing began on tablets, first of clay, then of wood. The next stage of development - before the invention of paper - the material means of information changed, that is, for the first time it was possible to visualize information by engraving words on stone. This has given a dynamic meaning to information and communication.

The paper phase of information technology began in 12th century China. Shortly afterwards, the paper became an object of industrial production in European countries.

With the advent of paper, a new stage of information began: the most acceptable carrier of information - the book.

The ensuing period played a major role in the development of information technology. The separation of trade and handicrafts came from the city post office, and later the private post office (Western Europe), and in the 16th and 17th centuries the central royal post office (France, Sweden, England, etc.). Thanks to this sustainable communication, more people began to be involved in information activities, and it spread to larger regions.

The publication of the book in Germany was a huge breakthrough in the development of information technology. This case brought him publicity. In essence, this has become a new stage of scientific and technological progress. The emergence of the scientific and technical term has led to qualitative changes in the field of information technology, and the publication of numerous books, magazines, newspapers, maps, and technical drawings has led to quantitative changes.

Until the second half of the XIX century, the basis of information technology was a pen, ink and an accounting book, and communication (communication) work was carried out by sending a package (envelope with official documents). The productivity of information processing is very low, and each letter is copied separately, manually. There was no information other than the book that was added to the account to make a decision.

A new stage in the development of information technology in connection with the technical revolution of the late XIX century was the discovery of photography (1879), telegraph (1832), telephone (1876), radio (1895) as a form of sustainable international communication.

At the end of the 19th century, "mechanical" technology replaced "hand" information technology. The invention of the typewriter, the telephone, the dictaphone, the improvement of the public mail system - all this led to significant changes, first in information processing technology, and then in productivity. In essence, mechanical technology has led to the formation of organizational structure in existing institutions.

In the 1940s and 1960s, new technologies emerged, such as electric typewriters, plain paper copiers, and portable dictaphones. It is these tools that have improved management performance by increasing the quality, quantity and speed of document processing. Many modern institutions have begun to operate on information technology tools based on electricity-adapted technology.

From the second half of the 60s of the twentieth century, "electronic" or "computer" technologies emerged and changed not only the form of information, but

also its content. Information has become one of the most valuable types of products that human beings consume, both in terms of content and quantity.

A new stage in the development of the information revolution began in the second half of the twentieth century. During this period, with the development of information technology, the speed of transmission of information using electromagnetic waves increased by a million times compared to oral speech.

It is well known that management information technology must have at least three important components in information processing: accounting, analysis, and decision making. The implementation of these on computers became increasingly popular, as the "sea of papers", which contained countless pieces of information, was expanding.

Information technology has become an active productive force, and artificial intelligence has created the opportunity to solve qualitatively new tasks of technical development. The special importance of a mechanized dynamic information system has put the problem of creating more modern electric computers and related technologies at the forefront of public life.

The history of the development of the mechanism of information interaction between humans, and now between man and machine, provides a basis for understanding information technology as a single integrated system of development of all fields of science.

The current stage of development of information technology dates back to the early 90s of the twentieth century. By this time, information technology had laid the groundwork for the emergence and functioning of the digital economy. At the same time, this period can be considered as successful years in the field of digital economy, as by this time the use of digital technologies has accelerated, local, regional and global networks have emerged and developed rapidly.

We believe that the following issues need to be addressed for the Republic of Uzbekistan in the development of information technology.

- in the process of continuous improvement of the latest information techniques and technologies, their use only for the sake of peace and interethnic harmony;

- to mobilize the results of existing information technologies in each country for the development of the nation, the further strengthening of national and universal values;

- pay special attention to the formation of complete, accurate, strategic information in the world and the problems of their rational use;

- protection of information security and prevention of its use for malicious purposes, etc.

We will try to cover our views on these issues in more detail in our next work.

Conclusions and suggestions.

Based on the above:

1. When it comes to information technology, it should be noted that information is involved both as a material and as a product.

2. Information technology is a process that uses a set of tools and methods to collect, process, and transmit information to obtain information about a new feature of an object, process, or event.

3. Information technology is the first foundation of the transition to the digital economy. It would be more accurate to call it digital information technology, because information technology is based on relevant numbers.

4. Information technology is the basis for the transition to the digital economy.

5. Information technology is becoming the driving force of society, and artificial intelligence is creating opportunities for the development of modern technology to solve qualitatively new tasks.

6. During the years of independence, our country has undergone profound changes in the field of science, including information technology, as a result of which there is a great need for the transition to a digital economy in all sectors of our national economy.

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